

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF THE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE CRIME OF ESCAPING A VEHICLE

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Abstract: This article deals with the concept of qualifying crimes and, more specifically, the crime of vehicle theft. It discusses the rules for qualifying an act under Article 267 of the Criminal Code and provides suggestions for correct legal assessment of vehicle theft crimes.

Keywords: Vehicle, qualification, qualification of crime, evading vehicles, purpose of robbing a vehicle.

The changes in the field of law today serve the interests of the people which can be observed by the reforms implemented in the field of judicial law in our country. The president of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, highlighted in his speech at the 72nd session of the United Nations General Assembly on September 19, 2017, that the primary goal of the deep reforms implemented in all areas is to prioritize human interests which builds a democratic and just society¹. As a result, investigative and judicial bodies are tasked with ensuring the full protection of human rights and freedoms. This includes accurately qualifying the actions of individuals who have committed socially dangerous acts, conducting full legal assessment and holding them responsible for their actions. This can only be achieved by following proper legal procedures.

The proper classification of crimes is a crucial element in the application of criminal law. The investigation of criminal cases, court proceedings, and determining the appropriate type and level of punishment all hinge on correctly identifying and classifying the crime. There are varying interpretations of the classification of crimes among legal scholars in criminal law theory. V.N. Kudryavtsev states that "to classify a crime means to provide a legal assessment of the act, specifying the appropriate criminal-legal norm that reflects the characteristics of the crime."² Based on this perspective, professor M.Kh Rustambaev suggests that the concept of crime classification is used both in a broader and narrower sense. In the narrow sense, classification refers to the legal evaluation of a socially dangerous act according to criminal legal norms. In the broader sense, classification involves a logical process, and it is the responsibility of certain individuals to determine whether a socially dangerous act has the necessary elements to be classified as a crime under the provisions laid out in the Special Part of the Criminal Code.³

According to Professors R. Kabulov and A.A. Atajonov, the qualification of crimes is to

¹ Mirziyoev Shavkat Miromonovich's speech at the 72nd session of the United Nations General Assembly on September 19, 2017. <https://www.uzavtoyul.uz/cy/post/uzbekiston-prezidenti-shavkat-mirziyoyev-bmt-bosh-assambleyasining-72sessionida-nutq-sozladi.html>(Time of reference to the electronic resource: 15.02.2023)

² Kudryavtsev V. N. General theory of qualification crimes. - M., 2001. - S. 4.

³Rustambaev M.Kh. Course of criminal law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Special part. - T., 2011. - B.11.

determine and legally strengthen the complete compatibility of the signs of the committed act with the signs of the criminal structure provided for in the Special Part of the Criminal Code.⁴

Thus, as a result of the qualification of any crime, a conclusion is drawn as to which norm of the criminal law can be applied in a particular case.

In our opinion, it is important to first establish whether the elements of a socially harmful act and the elements of a crime as defined in the special section of the Criminal Code are fully compatible with each other through the elements of the crime itself, such as the object, objective aspect, subject, and subjective aspects of the offense. A general rule in criminal law is that classifying an action according to a certain article or part of an article is straightforward. However, some norms defined in the Criminal Code may refer to not only one, but multiple crimes, such as carjacking.

Based on this, it can be concluded that stealing a vehicle is considered a complex crime. On December 26, 2016, the Law of Republic of Uzbekistan (LPU)-416⁵ was passed to amend and add to some legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This law amended Article 206 of the Criminal Code by adding "g" to the second part of the article, which includes theft or robbery committed with the intent to steal a vehicle. In addition, "v" was added to the third part of the article, which involves invasion with the intent to steal a vehicle.

After these changes, if someone steals a vehicle using theft, robbery, or invasion with the intent to rob it, only the relevant parts and clauses of this article will apply. This amendment ensures that the nature of the crime and its classification are more accurate, which is important for ensuring fair and just legal proceedings.

Overall, the text explains the importance of ensuring the compatibility of the elements of a crime and notes the changes made to the Criminal Code regarding carjacking. However, it could benefit from clearer language and organization to enhance comprehension.

. The circumstances surrounding carjacking often lead law enforcement agencies to face numerous difficulties and complications when attempting to classify the crime. These difficulties include misinterpretations of crimes related to driving away a vehicle, non-consideration of the subjective side of the crime, and incorrect qualification of the perpetrator's actions due to a lack of attention paid to their mental state. As a result, we would like to offer some recommendations regarding the correct classification of the crime of carjacking.

To do this, it is important to understand the concept of this crime, which is defined by the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 37 of December 20, 1996. According to paragraph 1 of the Criminal Code 267, the essence of carjacking is the act of evasion, which means moving from one place to another without the intention of stealing another person's vehicle.⁶

Based on the above definition, we can know that taking another person's vehicle without the purpose of robbery is qualified by the first part of this article. That is, we can understand that

⁴Qualification of crimes: a textbook for MIA higher education institutions / R. Kabulov, A. A. Otajonov, D. Yu. Payziev and others. – T.: Academy of Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2016. – B.8.

⁵ Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 26, 2016 No. LPU-416Law (Article 9).<https://lex.uz/docs/3084099> (Time of reference to the electronic resource: 15.02.2023)

⁶The Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 37 of December 20, 1996 "On judicial practice in the cases of vehicle hijacking" decision. Clause 1. <https://lex.uz/docs/1442544>

the purpose of the guilty person is to move and use and abandon vehicles without the purpose of robbery, which is the subject of Article 267 of the Criminal Code.

It is at this point that a question arises. How is the crime qualified if the vehicle was stolen by the guilty person for the purpose of robbery? In such situations, based on the method of committing the crime of taking away a vehicle for the purpose of robbery by the guilty party, paragraph "g" of the second part of this article is committed by theft or robbery with the purpose of robbing a vehicle, or the third part of this article Clause "v" is qualified with the corresponding clauses if it is committed by means of an invasion for the purpose of robbing a vehicle.

As we said above, it is important to know the structural elements of this crime in order to give a criminal-legal assessment of the crime of taking away a vehicle, to correctly qualify this norm. In particular, the motive and purpose of the person who committed the act provided for in Article 267 of the Criminal Code is of great importance in qualifying this crime.

Professor M.Kh. According to Rustambaev, while having the opportunity to use the vehicle while taking it away, the abandonment of the vehicle and other circumstances may indicate that it was not intended to rob it.

Also, Professor M.Kh. Rustambaev states that the following circumstances may indicate the presence of the guilty person's intention to steal a vehicle, i.e. changing the appearance of the vehicle (repainting, changing the number, re-bodying and other modifications); preparation of forged documents for use;

sell the vehicle; sell some parts; long-term use and so on⁷ stated that.

We agree with Rustambaev's opinion. After stealing a vehicle, the actual guilty person may not use the vehicle while having the opportunity to use it. They may choose to own the vehicle, sell it, sell it in parts, or install spare parts on other vehicles, among other actions. If the person abandons the vehicle in an unattended place or brings it back to the place where it was stolen, it indicates that they did not have the intention of stealing the vehicle. In such situations, it is correct to qualify it under Part 1 of Article 267 of the Criminal Code. However, if it is determined that the person's goal was to steal a vehicle, then it would be classified differently.

In our opinion, again in the qualification of this crime it should be taken into account that the fuel consumed while driving the stolen vehicle should not be considered as robbery, fuel should be considered as a source of power that drives the vehicle.

It can be seen from the above that in the qualification of the crime of taking away a vehicle, determining the motive and purpose of the guilty person ensures the correct qualification of the act.

Continuing with our recommendations, we would like to mention that one of the difficulties in the qualification of this crime is that in cases where the crime of carjacking is not completed, i.e., at the time of the attempt to commit this crime, it is considered to be the punishment for the crime of the guilty person.

⁷Comments on the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Special part/M. Rustambaev. - Tashkent: "Legal literature publish", 2021. - 504 p.

In such situations, the guilty person starts to carry out the actions of taking away the vehicle, and during the taking away of the vehicle, the criminal act of the guilty person is stopped independently by the law enforcement officers or the owner of the vehicle. It is in this situation that it becomes difficult to give a legal assessment to the act of the guilty person and to determine his motive.

Even in this situation, determining the purpose of the person ensures the correct qualification of the act. In a situation like the one above, the purpose of the person who committed the crime is determined based on the evidence collected during the investigation and his act is qualified.

During our research on court verdicts, we found that investigative bodies and judicial authorities sometimes qualified similar actions differently. This was often due to changes in the defendant's statements during the investigation and trial. For example, if the accused initially indicated that their intention was to rob a vehicle, the investigator might classify their actions under a relevant part of Article 267 of the Criminal Code. However, if the defendant later changed their testimony and denied any intent to rob the vehicle, the court might reclassify the offense as falling under Part 1 of Article 267, based on insufficient evidence of intent to rob. Unfortunately, such situations can result in false accusations and incorrect classification of the accused person's actions. In some cases, the investigative body may overqualify the offense by invoking heavier parts or clauses of relevant norms in the Criminal Code, only to later downgrade the charge during trial. These practices violate the accused person's rights and the principles of justice and responsibility for guilt in the Criminal Code. We have observed many such examples in investigative practice.

We would like to give our explanation below in order to eliminate the above situations and prevent such situations.

If it is not possible to determine the signs of the subjective side in the deed committed by the person, it is necessary to qualify the deed based on the signs of the objective side.

For example, if it is not possible to determine whether the person who attempted to commit the crime of stealing a vehicle has the intention of robbing this vehicle, we consider it appropriate to assess his actions based on the act he committed at that time.

We believe that the application of this definition to attempted vehicular offenses provides a proper characterization of the offense.

We have seen through the above examples that the motive and purpose of the criminal is important in qualifying the crime of taking away a vehicle.

Professors R. Kabulov and A. According to the Otajonovs, if, according to the situation of the case, a person has the intention to rob a vehicle after taking it away, the act should be classified under the set of crimes of taking away a vehicle (JK 267-m) and (JK 169-m)⁸league is shown.

⁸Criminal law Special part: Textbook. The second edition, revised and supplemented / Sh.T.Ikramov, R.Kabulov, A.A.Otajonov et al.; Responsible editor Sh.T. Ikramov - T.: Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2021. - 843. p.

We are professors R. Kabulov and A. Agreeing with the above opinion of Atajonov, we believe that it is appropriate to consider the following example as a fact that such actions are not fully appreciated in practice.

On January 16, 2023, the Samarkand District Court on criminal cases issued a verdict in criminal case No. 1-1402-2201/278. The defendant was Talibov Zafar Nabi, born in 2004, under Article 267, Part 2, Clause "g" of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. accused. Case details; Defendant Z. Talibov came to the car wash located in the "Kavchinon" neighborhood of Samarkand district on August 13, 2022, in order to escape with a car. settled and came to this car wash on August 14, 2022 at 08:30 to wash his car, took away the Nexia-3 car driven by O. Sadullaev for washing, and O. Taking advantage of the fact that Sadullaev had left his car, he took this car to the territory of Okdarya district. Defendant Z. Talibov drove this car for two days. When the car ran out of fuel, he replaced a car tire in the trunk of the car with fuel and poured this fuel into the car and drove it.

According to the decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 20, 1996, "Court practice on the cases of transporting vehicles, which considered the criminal action of the defendant Z. Talibov by the jury, the preliminary investigation body to be wrongly qualified by Article 267, Part 2, Clause "g" of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In paragraph 3, paragraph 2 of the Resolution No. 37, it is explained that if the culprit intended to rob a vehicle when he took away the vehicle, his actions should be qualified by paragraph "g" of the second part of Article 267 of the Criminal Code based on the nature of the act. .

According to the content of the law:

- abandoning the vehicle while it was possible to use it while escaping and other circumstances may indicate that there was no intention to extort it;
- the presence of the purpose of stealing a vehicle may be indicated by the following circumstances: changing the appearance of the vehicle (repainting, changing the number plate, re-bodying and other modifications) preparation of forged documents for use; sell the vehicle; sell some parts; indicated as long-term use and so on.

According to the circumstances revealed in the court investigation, on August 14, 2022, at 08:30, Z. Talibov took the "Nexia-3" car driven by O. Sadullaev for washing, and took this car to the territory of Okdarya district, after which the car was was driving in different places and on the night of August 15, around 10:00 p.m., he turned around and went out again, and in the village of "Kurilish" he was stopped in front of the car in a white "Neksiya-2" car, after which Z. Talibov suddenly set the car on fire and left the village. ran away at high speed through the streets and left the car he was driving on the side of the road. It can be seen that Z. Talibov drove the Nexia-3 state-marked car driven by O. Sadullaev for two days. However, Z. Talibov during this period O. Although he had the opportunity to use the "Nexia-3" car under Sadullaev's control, he abandoned the vehicle, changed the appearance of the vehicle, prepared forged documents for its use, sold the vehicle, used it for a long time, etc. Although Garchand, Z. Talibov changed the car tire in the trunk of the "Nexia-3" car driven by O. Sadullaev with gasoline fuel, according to his instructions, the purpose of taking the car away was not to rob the car, but

only because the car ran out of fuel. , that he replaced the car tire in the trunk of the car with fuel in order to refuel the car, the document was signed: Rajabov Nodirjon Tursunboltaevich, 16.01. He stated that if he had the intention of stealing the car or its parts and equipment, he

had enough time and that his purpose was only to drive the car. In this case, it cannot be assessed that the defendant Z. Talibov, driven by O. Sadullaev, took the "Nexia-3" car with the purpose of robbery by means of theft or robbery. There is no evidence to prove that the Nexia-3 car was taken away by theft or robbery for the purpose of robbery, therefore, the court panel found the criminal act of the defendant Z. Talibov under Article 267, Part 2, Clause "g" of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - considers it necessary to requalify for the part.

The defendant Z. Talibov was found guilty of committing the crime provided for by Article 267, Part 1 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. He was sentenced to 6 (six) years of imprisonment in accordance with Article 267, Part 1 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.⁹

We believe that the actions of the defendant Z. Talibov were reclassified by the Court to Article 267, Part 2, Clause "g", Article 267, Part 1 of the Criminal Code. Only the actions of Z. Talibov have not been fully assessed legally, the fact that the tire in the trunk of the vehicle was exchanged for fuel remains open. In our opinion, the defendant Z. Talibov's motive for robbing the car tire appeared after the defendant Z. Talibov took away the transport vehicle. In such a situation, the defendant Z. Talibov's actions and we believe that it should be evaluated as a set of crimes with Article 267, Part 1 and Article 169, Part 1 of the Criminal Code.

In conclusion, we have discussed the specific aspects of the crime of taking a vehicle and identified its problems and shortcomings in terms of qualification. Our recommendations aim to find a solution that is aligned with the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 approved by presidential decree(PD)-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 28, 2022.¹⁰Our suggestions prioritize the establishment of a people-friendly state that upholds human dignity and promotes the development of a free civil society. We believe that classifying crimes correctly and ensuring justice and the rule of law are crucial to the development of our country.

⁹ https://public.sud.uz/report/CRIMINAL_file:///C:/Users/PMM/Downloads/2141598.pdf

¹⁰ "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-60 of January 28, 2022 <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>(Time of reference to the electronic resource: 03.03.2023)

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